

**8 – SINFLARDA “HOME READING” MAVZULARINI
MUSTAHKAMLASH UCHUN QO'LLANILADIGAN METODIK
USULLAR: “HOME READING. THE PICTURE OF DORIAN GRAY”
MAVZUSI ASOSIDA O'RGANISH**

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Farg'ona viloyati Qo'shtepa tumani XTB tasarrufidagi 16-umumta'lim maktabi
ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

***Annotatsiya:** Yosh avlodni chet tillarida o'qitish hamda shu tillarda erkin so'zlasha oladigan mutaxassislarni tayyorlashni takomillashtirish negizida, yoshlarning jahon sivilizatsiyasi yutuqlari, shuningdek, butun dunyo axborot resurslaridan foydalanishlari, xalqaro hamkorlik va muloqotni rivojlantirish uchun shart - sharoitlar yaratish asosiy maqsad qilib qo'yiladi. Shu sababdan ham chet tillarini o'rganish bugungi kunning asosiy talabi bo'lib qoldi. Chet tilida gapirishga o'rgatish – bu chet tili darslarining asosiy maqsadi sanalanadi.*

Chet tillarini o'rgatishda o'sha xalqning hikoya va badiiy asarlaridan foydalanish orqali o'quvchilarning nutqini rivojlantiriladi hamda turli xalqlarning madaniyatini, qadriyatlarini xurmat qilib, to'g'ri baholay olishida yordam beradi.

Biz tavsiya qilmoqchi bo'lgan mavzuning asosiy maqsadi yuqori sinflarni chet tili darslarida ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalar va interfaol usullardan foydalangan holda o'quvchilarning milliy va xorij adabiyotiga bo'lgan ijobiy munosabatni rivojlantirish hisoblanadi. 8-sinflarda chet tillarni o'rgatish ta'limi unda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarning tadbiq etilishiga oid ilmiy - metodik tavsiyalar bilan boyitildi.

Kalit so'zlar: *interfaol usul, kommunikativ metod, autentiv matn, aqliy hujum(brainstorming), “Matching” usuli, “Idrok xaritasi”, “Konseptual xarita”, “Kartografiya konsepsiyasi”, “Intellekt xarita”*

Dastlab interfaol usul nima ekanligi haqida tushuncha berib o'tsak. Interfaol inglizcha so'z bo'lib, «interact»: «inter» - o'zaro va «act» - harakat

qilmoq), ularni umumlashtirganda esa, «Interfaol» - o‘zaro harakat qilmoq ma’nosini anglatadi. «Interaction» - hamkorlikni (boshqalar bilan) bildiradi. Ya’ni, o‘qitishning interfaol uslublari – bilish va kommunikativ faoliyatni tashkil etishning maxsus shakli bo‘lib, unda ta’lim oluvchilar bilish jarayoniga jalb qilingan bo‘ladilar, ular biladigan va o‘ylayotgan narsalarni tushunish va fikrlash imkoniyatiga ega bo‘ladilar.

Interfaol usul - bu o‘qituvchi va o‘quvchilar o‘rtasida o‘zaro hamkorlik tufayli dars samaradorligini oshirish, yangi darsni o‘qituvchining mustaqil harakati, mulohaza, bahs - munozaralar orqali o‘rganish, qo‘yilgan maqsadga o‘zi mustaqil erishish, mikrogruphlarda javob topishga harakat qilishidir, ya’ni o‘quvchi fikrlaydi, yozadi, gapiradi, tinglaydi, eng asosiysi o‘zi faol ishtirok etadi. Interfaol o‘qitish usullari ayniqsa, amaliy mashg‘ulotlarda yaxshi samara beradi.

O‘qituvchining pedagogik jarayondagi asosiy vazifasi – boshqaruvchilik. U shaxsning shakllanishi, rivojlanishi, bilim olishi va tarbiyalanishi jarayonini boshqaradi. Boshqarish bu – yo‘naltirish, vazifa qo‘yish, o‘rgatish, yordam berish, qo‘llab – quvvatlash, maslahat berish, rahbarlik qilish, kuzatish, talab qilish va ko‘rsatma berishdir.

Kommunikativ metod asosida yaratilgan darsliklardagi mavjud matnlar autentivligi bilan eski darsliklardan farq qiladi. Eski darsliklardagi matnlar faqatgina darslik mualliflari tomonidan yozilgan bo‘lar edi. Autentiv matn tushunchasi ostida original va aynan yozma yoki og‘zaki ko‘chirilgan nusxa tushuniladi.

Tajribalar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, o‘quvchilarni matnlar bilan tanishtirish, turli lingvistik mushohadalar orqali matn ma’nosini tushuntirish xorijiy tillarni o‘qitishda samarali usul bo‘lib kelmoqda.

Quyida biz berilgan mavzuga oid bir nechta interfaol usullarni ko‘rib chiqamiz:

Belgilangan dars mashg‘uloti mavzusi “Home reading. The picture of Dorian Gray”. Dars mashg‘ulotida qanday interfaol usullardan foydalangan bo‘lar edingiz? Ushbu mashg‘ulot oldindan uyda mustaqil o‘qib kelish uchun

beriladi. Shuning uchun matn mavzusi bilan o‘quvchi oldindan tanish bo‘ladi va mustaqil fikr yuritib, og‘zaki hikoya qilib berishga tayyor bo‘ladi.

1. “Aqliy hujum”(Brainstorming) usuli.

1. Have you ever read a short story?
2. Have you ever drawn a picture?
3. Have you ever heard about Oscar Wilde?

Ushbu rasmni qayerda va qachon uchratgansiz? Where and when did you see this picture? Kabi savollar berib ular qanday bilimga ega ekanliklarini bilib olishimiz mumkin.

2. Matnni abzatlarga bo‘lish.

Bo‘lingan abzatlarni guruhlarda ma‘nosiga ko‘ra tartibli joylashtirish. Bunda o‘quvchilar o‘zlari guruhlarda mustaqil bajarishlari yoki belgilangan muddatda eshitish orqali joylashtirishlari mumkin.

- A. (‘ The Picture of Dorian Gray’ by Oscar Wilde was first published in Lippincott’s Monthly Magazine on June 20, 1890. Later, Wilde was asked to edit this version, and it was published again in April 1891. The story is often incorrectly called ‘ The Portrait of Dorian Gray’ .)
- B. In his London studio, artist Basil Hallward is finishing his latest portrait of a young man. Although Lord Henry asks about the young man’s name, Basil keeps it a secret but later says that the subject of the portrait is Dorian Gray.
- C. Lord Henry immediately begins to offer Dorian a lot of money. He wants Dorian to sell his soul. He explains to Dorian that he will stay as young as he looks in the portrait and instead of him his image in the portrait will become older. Dorian agrees because he is afraid to be old. He wishes he could stay young and beautiful. Since that time the portrait begins to live its own life. Lord Henry also tells Basil that if he burns the portrait Dorian will be killed.

- D. Dorian fall in love with a young actress, Sibyl Vane. She play a different role at each night’s performance. Dorian likes her performance more than the actress herself. They want to get married. Lord Henry and Basil are very surprised. Happy Sibyl discusses her wedding with her family. Her mother does not have much money and she does not want her daughter to marry Dorian because she thinks he is poor. But Dorian is rich.
- E. One day Dorian attends Sibyl’s performance with Lord Henry and Basil, but the performance is terrible. Sibyl tells Dorian that she can no longer act well, because he has shown her a beautiful reality. Dorian is surprised by her poor acting. He tells her that he does not love her anymore, and he returns home.
- F. To his surprise, the face in his portrait becomes very cruel. He thinks that his wish to stay young is coming true, so he wants to be good so that both he and the portrait can remain young. So the next day he wants to apologize to Sibyl and marry her after all.
- G. However, he is too late: Sibyl dies at the theatre that night. Dorian first feels sad, but then he thinks that it is a wonderful entertainment and the last act of her play. Dorian and Lord Henry spend the evening at the opera.
- H. Basil arrives and says that Dorian has a moral problem. But Dorian does not think about Sibyl or her family; he wants to talk only of happy things. The next day, he moves his portrait to the attic, to which Dorian has the only key.
- I. Several years pass and Dorian lives a life organised by Lord Henry. While the face in the portrait has turned ugly, Dorian stays young and beautiful. People say that Dorian is not a moral person, but he does not pay attention.

- J. Finally, when he is thirty-eight years old, Dorian shows the portrait to Basil, who asks Dorian to try to be good again. Instead, Dorian kills Basil and destroys his body.
- K. Six months later, while looking at the portrait, Dorian decides to damage it with the knife he used to kill Basil. Soon after, Dorian’s servants and a police officer find an old, ugly man lying dead on the floor in front of a portrait of a young and beautiful Dorian.

3. “Tarjimasini mosla” (Matching)usuli

Avval berilgan matndan yangi so‘zlarni topib, gap mazmunidan tarjimasini moslaydilar. Bunda o‘quvchilarga ma’lum vaqt berilishi kerak bo‘ladi.

- | | |
|------------------------------|---|
| 1. Portrait - | a. keep hidden from others |
| 2. keep it a secret - person | b. painting, drawing, or photograph of a person |
| 3. immediately- | c. making someone feel unhappy |
| 4. instead of - | d. when someone performs a play |
| 5. Play a different role- | e. after a long period |
| 6. performance - | f. when something else is used |
| 7. cruel - | g. to damage something so badly |
| 8. come true – | h. act out |
| 9. several years pass – | i. at once |
| 10. destroy - way | j. if the wishes or dreams happen in the way |

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
B	A	i	F	H	D	C	j	e	G

- 4. Matn bilan ishlash usuli. Nuqtalar o‘rnini to‘ldirishdan foydalansa bo‘ladi. Berilgan matnning orasidagi so‘zlar, raqamlar yoki so‘z birikmalari tushirib

qoldiriladi. O‘quvchilar matnni eshitib tushirib qoldirilgan so‘zlarni yozishlari kerak bo‘ladi. Tinglash qobiliyatini rivojlantiradi. Misol uchun, *In his studio, artist Basil Hallward is finishing his latest portrait of a young man. Although asks about the young man’s name, Basil keeps it a secret but later says that the subject of the portrait is Lord Henry immediately begins to offer Dorian a lot of money. He wants Dorian to sell his soul. He explains to Dorian that he will stay as young as he looks in the portrait and instead of him his image in will become older. Dorian agrees because he is afraid to be old. He wishes he could stay young and beautiful. Since that time the portrait begins to live its own life. Lord Henry also tells that if he burns the portraitwill be killed. Dorian fall in love with a young actress, She play a different role at each night’s performance. Dorian likes her more than the actress herself. They want to get married. Lord Henry and Basil are very surprised. Happy Sibyl discusses her wedding with her family. Her does not have much money and she does not want her daughter to marry Dorian because she thinks he But Dorian is rich.*

5. “Idrok xaritasi” (conceptual map) metodi

“Idrok xaritasi” (Konseptual xarita) adabiyotda turli nomlar bilan uchraydi: “Idrok xaritasi”, “Konseptual xarita”, “Kartografiya konsepsiyasi”, “Intellekt-xarita” - fikrlarni taqdim qilish va bog‘lash usuli bo‘lib, u o‘quvchilarda tassavvur qilish va fikrlarni tizimlashtirish, o‘tganilayotgan mavzudagi bosh g‘oyalar yoki asosiy tushunchalarni, birlamchi tushunchalarni izohlashga yordam beruvchi ikkilamchi va uchlamchi g‘oyalar yoki tushunchalarni ajratish ko‘nikma va malakalarini shakllantirishga qaratilgan.

Taklif etilayotgan usul yangi bilim va axborotlarni konspektlashtirishning standart chizmasini ishlashga xizmat qiladi va darsning uzundan uzoq konspektini yozish yukidan xalos etadi.

6. Matnni abzatslarga bo'lish va har bir abzatsga sarlavha qo'yishni o'quvchilarga havola etish.

1. About the author of the story.
2. Opening the secret.
3. Withes about staying young and beautiful
4. Fall in love with
5. The death of the portrait

7. Matnni abzatslarga bo'lgan holda tarjima qilish va savol tuzish. Berilgan savol matn ichida mavjud bo'lsa, to'g'ri (True) yoki ma'lumot noto'g'ri berilgan bo'lsa Noto'g'ri (False) belgilari qo'yiladi. O'qituvchi oldindan yozib kelgan tarqatma savollarni beradi. O'quvchilar guruhda ishlab javoblarni muhokama qiladilar.

1. 'The picture of Dorian Gray' was written by Basil. _____
2. Basil keeps it a secret but later says that the subject of the portrait is Lord Henry. _____
3. Dorian falls in love with young actress. _____
4. Actress's family thought that Dorian was poor. _____
5. At the end of the story Dorian was killed by his own picture. _____

Xulosa

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisining IX sessiyasi (1997 yil 29 avgust) da qabul qilingan O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonunni va "Kadrlar tayyorlash milliy dasturi" mazmunida barkamol shaxs va malakali

mutaxassisni tarbiyalab voyaga yetkazish jarayonining mohiyati to‘laqonli ochib berilgan.

Yuqoridagi metodik tavsiyada 8- sinflarda xorijiy tillarni o‘qitishda va aynan adabiy matnlar bilan ishlash jarayonida zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va interfaol usullardan foydalanish to‘g‘risida qisqacha ma‘lumot berishga va zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni ta‘limga tadbiq etishning afzalliklarini yoritishga harakat qildik.

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